

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Ahmad Rufai
FIRST NAME: Shamsuddeen
PROGRAM CODE: DIFE
COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 1
INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
 The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
 The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
 The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access) (plagiarism rate 7%)
 The author used the following software: MSWord 2007 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing the basics (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
4. Literature review (EUCLID 2021, 17-23)
5. American vs. British English basic differences and influence of change (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
6. CMS crib sheet (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)
7. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 56-61)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

Euclid University requires doctoral students to take ACA-401D, International Academic Writing (Doctorate). This course equips students with the knowledge and skills needed to write academic papers of international standard and conform with EUCLID standard guidelines. EUCLID ACA-401D period one revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma aims to expose students to critical points that guide good academic paper writing. The course pack focused on essay writing, plagiarism, literature review, style guide, the difference between American vs. British English, Rule of thumbs for writing paper, sample corrections to paper, CMS Crib Sheet, and Latin abbreviation & expressions. The course material includes a video that provides a practical guide on formatting documents in Microsoft Word and how to use a style in words.

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2) ESSAY WRITING THE BASICS

The ACA-401D period one coursepack mentioned, “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 1). Over the years, I have realized that concepts and ideas are accepted and better understood if presented with facts to support the viewpoints. The writer identified the points through reading and research in the essay question areas. Although essay writing is extensive work, starting the job early and making an essay plan will help write a good essay. I agree with the idea of “Work out your initial thoughts and ideas about the topic and write a preliminary essay plan to help guide your research” (EUCLID 2021, 1). The course pack highlighted the importance of researching the essay topic by reading and reviewing previous essay questions; as a doctoral student, I will have to check other people’s work to complete my dissertation. Writing the essay, producing a draft will allow the writer to structure the paper in such a way that will enable a logical flow of facts that will answer the essay question. A good essay should consist of an introduction, body, and conclusion.

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I have learned in the course pack that “All academic essays must contain references” (EUCLID 2021, 4); I am now familiar with different referencing styles and will be applying the most suitable one based on the EUCLID guidelines. Whenever I complete the essay draft, I will edit it. Academic essay writing always requires several revisions.

3) PLAGIARISM

My professional training as an Investment manager requires me to abide by the standard of professional conduct; one aspect of the standard is avoiding plagiarism in preparing research reports or conclusions of the analysis. “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 5). I feel thrilled ACA-401D coursepack period one is exposing me to a concept that will strengthen my professional and academic work. The academic paper involves reviewing other people’s work to establish evidence to support an argument, the course material identified proper citing as a method of avoiding plagiarism. Citing is done as in-text citing or a list of work cited. EUCLID ACA-401D requires students to use in-text citation when writing a response paper.

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In the coursepack, it reads that In-text citation “refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself” (EUCLID 2021, 6). List of work cited is another way of avoiding plagiarism, “It is the ‘bibliography’ or the ‘references’ listed at the end of the book” (EUCLID 2021, 10).

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Although I will be using other people’s previous work while writing an essay, the EUCLID coursepack has provided me with methods like citation, which involves presenting the point as presented by another author in between quotation marks and citing the author. An essay writer can reproduce the idea of an author in his words through paraphrasing, but most ensure accurate representation of the author’s view. While I

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appreciate the importance of citation to avoid plagiarism, I am happy to learn that common knowledge needs not to be cited.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPER

I have learned it is vital to introduce the thesis appropriately. The coursepack noted to “state the main thesis of your paper at (or near) the beginning” (EUCLID 2021, 14). After introducing my thesis, I will present the idea clearly to be easy for the reader to follow. The coursepack stated, “When you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right” (EUCLID 2021, 16). I entirely agree with this and will surely put it to practice.

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5) LITERATURE REVIEW

Usually, a literature review involves reviewing prior research work that highlights knowledge about a particular topic. As a doctoral student, the course material has prepared me to write a literature review for an academic paper. The use of apostrophes has always been confusing to me. However, my study of the ACA-401D course pack has taught me the essential rule that states apostrophe serves as a possessive or constriction function in writing.

6) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH BASIC DIFFERENCES AND INFLUENCES OF CHANGE

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Even though the British introduced the English language to America, American English is more widely used now; I use more American English during writing or conversation. The course has taught me that there are ways in which American and British English are different; basically, they differ in Spelling, Grammar, and Vocabulary. I agree that “American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with “educated” or “scientific” English.” (EUCLID 2021, 27). Some words have different spelling, but people pronounce them the same way; this can be seen in the word Color in American English but is spelled as colour in British although, all have the same pronunciation.

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7) CMS CRIB SHEET

I dedicated a lot of time to studying the portion of the coursepack that discusses the CMS Crib Sheet; because the EUCLID student orientation document mentioned students are required to use the Turabian rule of style. The course material mentioned, “While sometimes reference is made to a “Turabian style,” this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006.” (EUCLID 2021, 49). I am impressed with including

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abbreviations and acronyms among CMS Crib Sheet content. The development of chat messages, email, and other technological innovations has increased abbreviations in writing in our day-to-day lives. In my opinion, one of the objectives of academic writing is the reader's understanding, so the essay should be clear and concise devoid of abbreviation. Writers should not use abbreviations frequently. However, writers can use abbreviations in tables, honorifics, or parentheses.

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The material also emphasizes that the acronym is acceptable if the full name is used first in writing with the acronym in parenthesis.

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8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I took science subjects during my secondary school; this has introduced me to Latin words and expressions. However, ACA-401D has further deepened my knowledge of Latin abbreviations and expressions. I have learned it is better to use plain language in writing, but a writer can use Latin abbreviations in footnotes and bibliographies. The course material reminded me of the a.m. and p.m. terms we use to reference morning and afternoon time frames are Latin abbreviations of ante meridiem and post meridiem.

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9) CONCLUSION

After working for several years in my professional field, most of my writing is shaped by my professional work. There is a difference between professional writing and academic writing. My engagement with ACA-401D coursepack period one has refreshed my knowledge of academic writing; as a EUCLID doctoral student, this has improved my skills and will help me produce a quality academic paper that will follow international standards.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.